

Household district	Study Number	Household Identification Number

ASSENT FORM

STUDY TITLE

4. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi

Informed Assent Form for Project Participants 8-18 years of age

We are doing a research study about transmission of bacteria around a household. This research study is a way to learn more about people, animals and the environment. If you decide that you want to be part of this study, you will be asked to take part in an interview with a researcher and to provide one stool sample.

There are some things about this study you should know. The project team will visit your house twice in the first week. The sampling will then be repeated one and six months after the first visit. We plan to carry out interviews and collect samples from the humans and animals in the household, as well as the environment around the household.

Not everyone who takes part in this study will benefit. A benefit means that something good happens to you. We think these benefits might be that if any humans or animals in the household are carrying harmful bacteria we will detect this during the study. In this case harmful means bacteria which may potentially make you ill. Once the study is finished, we will report the results and offer any useful advice to you, to prevent you from becoming ill.

When we are finished with this study we will write a report about what was learned. This report will not include your name or that you were in the study.

You do not have to be in this study if you do not want to be. If you decide to stop after we begin, that's okay too. Your parents or guardians know about the study too.

If you decide you want to be in this study, please sign your name or place a thumbprint in the box to the right.

I, _____, want to be in this research study.

(Sign your name here/thumbprint)

(Date)

Confirmation of Impartial Witness:

I, _____, confirm that _____ has agreed to take part in the above research study

Signature _____ Date: _____

Signature of staff collecting the assent: _____ (Date) _____

